

The Ancient Rhythm that United Continents

Dan C. Baciu finds evidence that music has united the globe for thousands of years.

A day begins. The sky gradually brightens. The stars disappear. Then, as if by ancient ritual, the first rays of sun break over the horizon and drench the clouds in golden light. Only a little poetic license is needed to compare these colourful clouds to fiery celestial horses.

The image of the cloud-horses is rooted in antiquity, appearing thousands of years ago in a hymn dedicated to the Vedic goddess of dawn, Ushas. The chorus calls her, 'you, horse tamer, wellborn, rise!' Today, this hymn dedicated to Ushas has become part of a remarkable cultural heritage, the Rigveda – a holy scripture to more than a billion Hindus. To be precise, Ushas has entered this heritage from an earlier, prehistoric substrate of shared Old Indic and European ancestry. Because of these origins, her name is also found in English, echoed in the etymologically cognate 'Easter', which likewise celebrates the beginning of a natural cycle.

Growing out of this unique context, the Rigveda stands out through its excellent conservation. Ancient commentaries even explain how the Rigveda was initially sung, around 1500 to 1200 BCE. Yes... it was sung! The chorus 'you, horse tamer, wellborn, rise!' is a translation of 'sījāte āsvasūṅṛte'. The rhythm of these words is '...DOO-DOO-DOO-do-DOO-do-DOO!' With the melody added on top, it would have become something like '...DOO-DOO-DEE-do-DEE-do-DEE!' The same music also fits other verses, for example, 'lights illuminate the sky' – 'rōcante rocanā divi'.

I first learned about the Rigveda as a teenager attending linguistics classes at my hometown university. I loved music and poetry, and the Rigveda was something I didn't want to miss. Then, I made an unlikely discovery. It seemed an incredible testimony to the power of music. I discovered a connection between the Rigveda and something else.

In the 20th century, archaeologists working on the eastern coast of the Mediterranean unearthed something that caught my attention: the oldest known musical score,

dating from around 1400 BCE. This score contains a hymn dedicated to Nikkal, a Near Eastern goddess of fertility. Perhaps Nikkal's presence in the Near East doesn't sound unexpected, at first. She is Near Eastern, after all. Yet, what if I say that her music connects her to India?

The cadence '...DOO-DOO-DEE-do-DEE-do-DEE!', which is repeatedly found in the Rigveda, also concludes Nikkal's hymn. Furthermore, her hymn has a second cadence, midway in the composition. The melody goes '...DOO-dedo-DOO-do-DOO-DEE!' It's a much more unique melody. To modern ears, the rising last syllable could resemble a question. Yet this melody, too, connects Nikkal's hymn to the Rigveda. For example, Ushas is described to come without fail, rising in the east, and holding aloft the flame of knowledge. In doing so, she has the power to shine brightly because 'she follows natural laws', that is, 'ṛtāsya pānthām ānu eti sādhu', which has the very same cadence '...DOO-dedo-DOO-do-DOO-DEE!'

The question remains: Are these musical matches a true cultural connection or a very rare chance encounter? To test this, I performed a comprehensive computer-aided analysis of all ~40,000 verses of the Rigveda.

I started by focusing on rhythmic patterns, which demonstrated that the two cadences of Nikkal's hymn are also the two most frequent cadences of the Rigveda in its entirety. One in five verses of the Rigveda end with the two rhythms from the Mediterranean.

When I added the melody on top of the rhythm, an even more tantalising picture emerged. The two cadences of Nikkal's hymn are the two most common cadences specifically among the oldest Rigvedic material. This makes sense. Music composed around 1400 BCE in India and in the Mediterranean shared both rhythm and melody. By comparison, later Rigvedic compositions preferred different melodies, reflecting the changing

prosodic style, leading up to how the Rigveda is sung today.

My analysis also contains a randomised test, which provides an additional detail. The likelihood of finding such a close musical match by chance is lower than one in a million. It is as good as impossible. There must have been a musical connection between the Near East and the Rigveda – this extraordinary Indo-European heritage.

Today, we know that music has wings. In a day's time, music from India can reach the whole world. Many people believe that this is a uniquely modern phenomenon, facilitated by radio, television and social media. My discovery tells a different story. Music has united continents for thousands of years.

History helps further elucidate the case. The rhythmic cadence '...DOO-dodo-DOO-do-DOO-DOO!' resurfaces in later poetry, being prominently featured in the 'sapphic verse', utilised by Sappho on the Greek island of Lesbos, then by Horace in Rome and much later by Hölderlin in Germany. Thus, this cadence echoes through the finest Greek, Latin and German poetry. It even finds its way into the U.S. national anthem. The lyrics begin with 'O say can you see, by the dawn's early light, what so proudly we hailed?' Among these words, the last six, '...light, what so proudly we hailed' follow the very same rhythm '...DOO-dodo-DOO-do-DOO-DOO!' Here, the rhythm is easily traced back to a society inspired by Greek poetry. In parallel, during the years in which this dawn-themed hymn became a national anthem, a monumental female figure emerged in New York, holding aloft the flame of knowledge. Is she a daughter of Ushas?

The other rhythmic cadence '...DOO-DOO-DOO-do-DOO-do-DOO!' is even more remarkable. It's a simple rhythm, resembling that of a heart leaping with joy. The lyrics once pulsed, 'yes, you love, with all your heart!' Today, this heartbeat is heard across all continents.

Image: In 2026, the U.S.A. celebrates its 250th anniversary. The national anthem, banner and Statue of Liberty look back at a cultural history that is much older—at least 3,500 years. Image by Dan C. Baciu, copyright of the author, October 2025. Alternative text: The Statue of Liberty and stars, clouds at dawn resembling the banner of the U.S.A.

The rhythm of the national anthem of the U.S.A. connects it to the oldest musical score in the world, dating back 3,500 years and originating in the Near East.

Bio: As a child, Dan C. Baciu witnessed the 1989 Romanian revolution, which demonstrated the importance of culture in uniting people. Today, Baciu is a professor active across the United States and Europe. His research into ancient music has been featured on the *Science AAAS* weekly podcast.